

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES

Nuritdinova Kh.N.

Special defectologist of a secondary school 11, Namangan region

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Abstract. *The main goal of innovative activity is the development and application of new innovative technologies in special and inclusive education with disabilities. The article presents the types of art therapy technologies considered in modern pedagogical technology for the development of a child with disabilities as a creative person, transferring him from the type of reproductive activity to an independent search for methodological solutions, turning the teacher into a developer and author of innovative methods, introducing innovative teaching aids.*

Keywords: *disabled children, great ancestors, innovative methods, special and inclusive education, legal documents, art therapy.*

Relevance of the topic. It is important to suggest that the fact that people with disabilities make up a significant part of the population also indicates the need to pay more attention to the issue of ensuring them equal rights and opportunities.

According to the data, 1 billion or 15 percent of the world's population are people[1] with disabilities. In our country, there are about 1 million citizens[2] with disabilities.

It is worth mentioning that creating competitive conditions so that persons with disabilities have the opportunity to earn enough money to live through suitable work, so that they can live a comfortable life and, most importantly, feel like full members of society, and not be dependent on others, on the contrary, to achieve socio-economic equality with them is of great importance. It should be noted that in recent years, our country has been carrying out extensive work aimed at protecting human rights, including the rights of persons with disabilities, inclusive development, ensuring equal rights and opportunities for all segments of the population. At the same time, legal documents do not contain enough provisions guaranteeing the right of persons with disabilities to work on a competitive basis with others, and in some cases, effective mechanisms for ensuring this right remain uncertain. The relevance and necessity of issues of improving the legal mechanisms for the active participation of persons with disabilities in socio-economic life, the implementation of their labor rights and employment are substantiated by the following.

The first reason is that the employment rate of people with disabilities remains low. Despite the fact that national legislation provides for provisions on the protection of the labor rights of people with disabilities and the provision of benefits to them, due to the lack of development of effective legal mechanisms and the presence of some legal gaps, only 21.1 thousand people with disabilities are able to perform certain types of work in our country or 13 percent are declared as having a job. As of 2022, the average employment rate of people with disabilities is only 2 percent. These figures once again confirm that the issue of ensuring employment of people with disabilities is a pressing social problem.

Besides that, the implementation of children's rights varies by region and is influenced by factors such as gender, urban or rural residence, disability status, family income, and the language spoken at home. These differences highlight the need for targeted action to eliminate inequalities and ensure equal opportunities for all children. Eliminating regional differences, improving access

to services, and ensuring quality education and early access to children is a pressing issue and important for us, special educators.

Moreover, a positive trend in this regard has been observed in our country for several years. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PR-5217, dated August 9, 2021 "On measures to further improve the quality of medical and social services provided to persons with disabilities" provides for the rehabilitation of persons with disabilities, especially children, their modern prosthetic and orthopedic provision.

Certainly, a number of effective tasks have been set to provide rehabilitation devices and technical means, the introduction of information and communication technologies in this area. In particular, the equipment allocated to multidisciplinary specialized preschool educational organizations of Namangan region can serve as a vivid confirmation of this. Information on the coverage of 7 multidisciplinary specialized preschool educational organizations of Namangan region is presented in the form of a table. At present time 673 children are covered by diagnosis of 6 types of diseases. 408 of them are disabled children.

Definitely, education and upbringing of children with disabilities in Namangan region, taking into account their personal characteristics and in accordance with the decree of the President of October PD-486013, 2020 "On measures to further improve the education system and upbringing of children with special educational needs", on the education of children with disabilities, cooperation agreements have been concluded with the departments of health, labor and social protection of the region on issues of participation. In addition, good results can be achieved by combining the works of our great ancestors Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Muhammad Musa Khorezmi, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Imam Ismail Bukhari, Imam At Termizi, Mirza Ulugbek and Alisher Navoi lived and created in the past, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdulhamid Cholpon, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abdullah Avloni, Sadridin Ainiya, ideas, pedagogical thoughts and views set out in them, with today's education and training.

Methodology. It should be suggested that the main goal of innovative activity is development and education, that is, to develop a teacher as a creative person, to transfer him from the type of reproductive activity to an independent search for methodological solutions, to turn a teacher into a developer and author of innovative methods, to introduce innovative teaching aids. The art therapy method is considered a modern pedagogical technology in working with disabled children.

Art therapy is an important and effective method of ensuring the social and psychological well-being of a child in a kindergarten, in which children will reveal their best spiritual powers, enhance their personal development and dignity. Art therapy ("art" + therapy) is a form of psychotherapy and psychological correction that uses art and creativity for therapy. The main principle of art therapy is to give the opportunity to depict their inner experiences and feelings, whether it is a healthy child, a disabled child or an adult, and thereby successfully adapt them to life. For children with disabilities, the transition from the real world to the imaginary world, creating something independently contributes to the development of creative thinking and develops the child's creative abilities. Art therapy brings children and parents closer to the teacher, helps to better understand their feelings, helps to express their thoughts. Positive and negative possibilities of children's feelings towards their parents are revealed. This creates an opportunity to learn more about the inner experiences of children with disabilities, thereby developing their cognitive processes and showing their creative abilities. Besides that, in the educational process,

art helps therapists and teachers establish a trusting relationship with the child, interpret and diagnose the current situation. This technology is implemented in healthy children and children with disabilities in several ways, let's consider some of them:

- playing therapy, playing exercises occupy a special place in art therapy.

Playing exercises not only give a person pleasure, but also require creativity from him, direct him to creativity. The game helps a preschooler to realize himself as a person, increase self-esteem, respond to all negative internal experiences, reduce anxiety, guilt and worries.

- painting and practical art play an important role in art therapy.

The main advantage of art therapy is that it overcomes the barrier of internal limitations and opens the doors of confidence in the subconscious (thematic drawing, drawing on wet paper; monotypes, drawing using the paint blowing technique to reduce emotional arousal, etc.). In art therapy in correctional work with children, we use the following methods:

- wet paper drawing technique. Using the largest palette of colors, a drawing is applied to a wet sheet of paper using watercolors. You need to watch how the colors mix with each other, feel the emotions that arise during the observation. Later, the patterns formed on the sheet of paper are given a name.

- paint blowing technique. A water-soluble dye with a high percentage of water is applied to a sheet of paper using a tube and the resulting structure is inflated. It is important to use the largest possible color palette when performing the exercise. Upon completion of the task, the child tries to recognize and visualize the resulting image;

- laughter therapy (acting out nursery rhymes, reading funny poems, spending funny moments, acting out funny words). It is known that when a person laughs, 80 muscle groups work, the body is saturated with oxygen, endorphins are produced, the stress level decreases. In the process of laughter, the child performs breathing techniques, facial exercises with artificial stretching of the lips into a smile. This makes children activate their articulatory organs.

- music therapy - "music has a greater influence than wisdom and philosophy", said Beethoven. For this reason, music training in art therapy, music treatment (recording, listening to records, playing instruments, singing, others) has great effect.

Besides that, music therapy methods together with other art therapy methods allow correcting various emotional deviations and mental disorders in children. According to our grandfather Ibn Sina, high and low voices have their own meaning, different voices tenderly express certain meanings, high and low voices, especially musical voice or sound level, are of great importance for influencing a person's psyche. After this consideration, Ibn Sina emphasized the positive and negative impact of pleasant and unpleasant sounds on human health.

- fairy tale therapy - (fairy tales with logos: finger, articulation, phonetic, fairy tales for teaching literacy, fairy tales that promote the formation of coherent speech, lexical and grammatical fairy tales) - the use of fairy tales for the purposes of education, behavior correction, prevention of psychological deviations, the method of psychological and psychotherapeutic support is calculated. Fairy tale therapy is appropriate to consider as a technology for maintaining health, including overcoming fear, eliminating emotions in the psyche.

According to Australian scientist Brett, "A child is not only a small person, but also a special person. He sees the reflection of his dreams with the help of magical stories and fairy tales. The author strives to follow the example of positive heroes in order to solve problems without fear in his soul. In addition, fairy tales and stories instill courage and self-confidence in young souls.

This is very important for the stable formation of the child's psychology. A child who has lost self-confidence will not fight problems and will never succeed". Through a fairy tale, a child learns to distinguish between good and evil. A child who learns to overcome difficult and dangerous situations through the example of fairy tale heroes will grow up mentally and spiritually strong. He does not become depressed when faced with a difficult situation, believes that happy days will come after the problems are left behind. The most important thing is that a feeling of overcoming fear and not being afraid of difficulties is formed in the heart.

- drama therapy, correction through games that look like psychodrama, was founded by Jacob Moreno. He noted that participation in performances has a positive effect on the human psyche. Theatrical games activate memory, attention, will, emotional excitement, imagination and physical condition.

- sand (mud) therapy, this therapy was founded by Carl Jung, the purpose of which is to relieve internal tension. When a child works with dry and wet sand (mud), an aggressive child finds an outlet for his emotions, and an insecure child learns to control the situation, and clay helps children with an absent-minded and restless mind to focus their imagination. Children make different things from sand and increase their physical and mental activity. Building castles and houses from sand develops creative thinking, attention, overcomes fear, is reflected in pictures, creates feelings, gives freedom.

- kinesiotherapy, (derived from the English word "movement therapy"), treatment of children with disabilities using therapeutic and physical methods, this method is used in the rehabilitation of children and adults with one or more types of diseases of the musculoskeletal system.

Additionally, phototherapy, which is a solution to psychological problems, the role of phototherapy in personal growth and self-awareness is important. In this case, a person can take a photo of himself or work with ready-made pictures. Additional visual techniques, drawing and making a model from pictures will focus attention and strengthen memory.

Figure 3.2. Corrective processes using the latest technologies

Thus, innovative pedagogical technologies are closely related to all aspects of educational work in kindergartens. The classification of teaching and learning methods is constantly being modernized taking into account the innovations introduced into the education system.

What is more important, the use of interactive methods is an important issue for educators of preschool educational organizations, speech therapists, and music teachers. When using interactive methods, it is necessary to implement didactic principles in accordance with various goals and environments. This gives them the opportunity to speed up the process of preschool education, increase the responsibility of learning and speed up the educational process.

Result. The purpose of the activities of specialized preschool education organizations is aimed at preschool education of children with disabilities in physical development, their upbringing and rehabilitation, adaptation to society, correction of developmental deviations, ensuring their physical, mental and spiritual maturity. In particular, 673 children with mental, speech, visual, auditory and musculoskeletal disabilities are being brought up in the multidisciplinary specialized preschool educational institutions that have been preserved in Davlatabad, Torakorgon, Pop, Uychi and Yangikorgon districts. Children were admitted to specialized preschool educational institutions based on the conclusion of specialists throughout the year, depending on the number of vacancies in these institutions. In total, 7 multidisciplinary specialized preschool educational institutions in the region have a design capacity of 1,400 places and the capacity to cover children with physical or mental disabilities is 756 places. The total number of groups in these multidisciplinary specialized state preschool educational institutions is 63 for 6 different diagnoses, including:

- Children with "mental retardation".
- "Hearing-impaired" children.
- "Visually impaired" children.
- Children with "musculoskeletal disorders".
- "Speech-impaired" children.

In the current 2021-2023 years, the attention is paid to the analysis of children with developmental disabilities in multidisciplinary specialized preschool educational organizations of the region, the highest rates of children with mental development disorders range from 12% to 14.8%, and children with musculoskeletal disorders - from 22% to 28%.

Besides that, over these years, the rates of children with visual and speech impairments have remained virtually unchanged. A slight decrease in the number of children with mental retardation and hearing impairments has been noted.

Summary. Effective technologies have been selected for teaching children with disabilities. Advanced educational methods and technologies were introduced into the environment together with organizations and institutions responsible for choosing effective technologies in accordance with educational goals and ensuring the inclusiveness of the educational process. It was emphasized that the educational environment should be provided with financial and social protection systems. It was suggested about the necessary to form methods of their support through certain components (information, consultation, psychological support, medical care, temporary care of other relatives).

By concluding it is important to suggest that the use of interactive methods is an important issue for specialists of preschool educational organizations. By the time of using interactive methods, didactic principles are implemented in accordance with many goals and conditions,

which gives them the opportunity to speed up the process of preschool education, increase the responsibility of learning and speed up the educational process. Full data exchange means the creation of important monitoring and mechanisms to ensure the future academic performance of children. An important task is to analyze these educational and social protection systems.

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